

Overcoming Environmental Changes with Phytoplankton as Oxygen-Producing Agents in the Research River Estuary, West Kalimantan

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Protecting the environment is one of the obligatory tasks of every human being. This needs to be done to maintain the survival of humans, animals and plants. If not treated properly, there will be damage to nature and can threaten every living thing. The number of deviant human activities can have a negative impact on the preservation of nature. Later, these activities will also have an impact on environmental changes that will have a negative impact on living things. The occurrence of environmental changes can be caused by two factors, namely human factors and natural factors. Some human activities that can affect environmental changes, such as logging, building houses, and others. Forests are natural resources that make up about 30 percent of the land surface of the planet Earth. Unfortunately, along with the development of the times the trees in the forest are also shrinking due to logging. As we feel today, the number of development and forest function experts makes carbon emissions in the air increase.

Trees absorb carbon dioxide which is a greenhouse gas (a trigger for global warming) and also replace it as oxygen that humans and animals breathe. However, as development and logging activities carried out by humans reduce the number of trees, the impact of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere increases which causes the rich house effect and increases the earth's temperature. Global warming causes the temperature of the oceans and the earth's surface to increase, causing the melting of polar ice caps and rising sea levels. It also alters natural patterns of seasons and rainfall such as flash floods, excessive snow or desertification. As a result of these weather changes, agricultural production often experiences crop failures and increases the chance of forest fires due to the prolonged dry season (Lind, 1985). The main source of oxygen in the waters apart from the process of oxygen diffusion from the air is from the photosynthesis of phytoplankton, so the high oxygen content in the waters will characterize the high abundance of phytoplankton organisms in these waters (Patty, 2014).

Based on the results of the identification that has been carried out, found 82 types of phytoplankton that fall into 36 genera, 21 families, 7 orders, 3 classes belonging to 3 divisions, namely Bacillariophyta, Chlorophyta and Pirrophicophyta. A total of 56 types of phytoplankton were found in the east monsoon and 55 species in the west monsoon. The results of the measurement of physicochemical parameters in the Peniti River Estuary are still in good condition for the growth of phytoplankton. Chlorophyll is one of the parameters that determine primary productivity in waters. The distribution and the level of chlorophyll content are closely related to the oceanographic conditions of a waters (Mann and Lazier, 1991). Chlorophyll itself consists of three types, namely chlorophyll-a, b and c. These three types of chlorophyll are very important in the process of plant photosynthesis. The most dominant content possessed by phytoplankton is chlorophyll-a. Therefore, chlorophyll-a can be used as an indicator of water fertility (Junaidi et al, 2013).

According to Nybakken (1988). Bacillariophyceae are phytoplankton that are commonly found in waters and are large in size so they are often caught by plankton nets. Besides, Bacillariophyceae also have considerable resistance, as stated by Sulastri et al. (2002), that Bacillariophyceae have cell walls that are stronger against rainfall when compared to other groups such as Chlorophyceae. Class Dinophyceae found the most after diatoms. This is in accordance with Nontji (2006), Dinophyceae is a group. The most common phytoplankton found in the ocean after diatoms. In general, the content of chlorophyll-a during the east and

west seasons showed a varied range, ranging from 0.24 to 4.96 mg/m³ in the east monsoon with the category of moderate to moderate fertility (oligotrophic-mesotrophic) and in the west monsoon it ranged from 0,11-0.24 mg/m³ with low fertility (oligotrophic) Chlorophyll content in the east monsoon is suspected because of the high transparency of light, sunlight entering the waters is used by phytoplankton for photosynthesis. Generally, photosynthesis increases with increasing light intensity (Mann, 1982). Light is one of the factors that determine the distribution of chlorophyll-a in waters. The high content of chlorophyll-a in the east and west seasons is also thought to be due to the high composition of phytoplankton, namely from the Bacillariophyceae class, according to Sulastri et al. (2002) the increase in chlorophyll-a content is caused by the increased abundance of phytoplankton. The high content of chlorophyll is also associated with a decrease in the amount of nutrients, where the absorption of nutrients by phytoplankton causes a slowdown in the decrease in sinking of phytoplankton cells (Parsons and Takahashi, 1984).

Based on the explanation, we can conclude the ability of phytoplankton to carry out photosynthesis because it has a variety of chlorophyll, can produce oxygen and reduce the carbon dioxide content in the air. So that one day climate change which has a huge impact on the lives of all living things can be prevented and the state of nature can always be maintained in balance.

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